

Understanding Critical Software

For UKRI DRI

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About the SSI

The Software Sustainability Institute (SSI) was the first organisation in the world dedicated to improving software in research. It was founded in 2010 on the premise that helping individuals and institutions to understand the vital role that software plays in research would accelerate progress in every field of scientific and academic endeavour. The SSI has set itself the ambitious goal of transforming academic culture by establishing the principle that reliable, reproducible, and reusable software is necessary across all research disciplines. Recently, the SSI has moved into policy research to understand the landscape of research software use, focusing on skills, careers and infrastructure in academia and industry. This study was funded by phase 4 of the SSI under grant AH/Z000114/1.

About UKRI DRI

The UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) Digital Research Infrastructure (DRI) programme aims to create a coherent national digital research infrastructure that includes data infrastructure, compute, software, tools, networks, and skilled people. Its vision is a coherent state-of-the-art national digital research infrastructure that will seamlessly connect researchers, policymakers and innovators to the computers, data, tools, techniques and skills that underpin the most ambitious and creative research.

Introduction

This scoping study explores key issues around the critical software required to deliver the UKRI digital research infrastructure (DRI), and recommends what help UKRI could provide to support their investments. It also suggests next steps for future research to support DRI.

In a complex software ecosystem, understanding what software requires support and investment from UKRI is a complicated task. The Software Sustainability Institute (SSI) examined not just a list of software used by infrastructures, but considered a range of other issues. Our research questions were:

1. What software is used by the UKRI DRI infrastructures researched?
2. What should be considered as 'critical software' for UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure?
3. What are the risks to critical software for UKRI Digital Research Infrastructures?
4. How might audits support the infrastructures in preparing for and mitigating risks?

To begin to address these questions, the SSI conducted a short study over the course of six months starting in November 2024, interviewing staff from 3 Compute infrastructures (ARCHER2, JASMIN, Isambard-AI) and 3 Data infrastructures (Seshat - part of iDAH, the Programme Team from DARE-UK, PSDI) to ascertain details of their set up, funding, software stack, and audit/risk assessment processes, as well as their definitions of 'critical software' and opinions on the risks of disruption to the running of their infrastructures. Then, two focus groups were conducted with staff and users of the wider Compute and Data DRI community in order to corroborate and expand on the themes that arose in the interviews.

The report explores the software stacks of the 6 infrastructures (Appendix B), and provides illustrations of different 'critical software'. It looks at risks to software and also addresses the role of audits in understanding and preparing for risks to infrastructures. The report indicates how different parameters – types and size of infrastructure, users, available funding, and where the infrastructures were in their life cycle – influence the choices of software in use, and what this means for the risks to the infrastructures.

¹We spoke to the DARE-UK Programme Team. The DARE-UK programme have funded five Driver Projects to inform the design of a UK-wide network of trusted research environments (TREs), as well as starting to fund a series of activities to start assembling and testing the digital infrastructure required for research to tackle complex societal challenges.

Key Findings, Discussion & Recommendations

Key findings

- Infrastructures provided us with an indication of their **software stacks** (see [Appendix B](#)).
- **'Critical software'** was defined in two ways:
 - There being **no viable alternative** – discussed in relation to the cost or effort required to switch. Concerns here were tied to the resources that infrastructures had to address software challenges.
 - The **negative consequences** of software no longer working. This was discussed as affecting either the whole or part of the software stack, being an imminent consequence or at sometime in the future, and in relation to how much each person is affected vs. how many people are affected.
- Key **risks** to critical software were identified as being related to:
 - Limited or no **maintenance** from developers or communities.
 - A lack of internal **skilled staff** to support/maintain software.
 - **Licensing** changes.
 - Cost of **support** from commercial providers.
 - Changes in **governance**.
 - **Security** failures.
 - Incorrect/immature **code**.
- **Audits** were of value to those infrastructures that had conducted them, with many participants understanding their value in revealing the risks to critical software. Many wanted support in conducting audits. Infrastructures of different sizes and at different points in the life cycle require different kinds of audit.

Discussion

We found that it was a challenge to establish a comprehensive list of **software** used by the UKRI DRI infrastructures we interviewed. The details of infrastructure

software we have (Appendix B) were obtained from participants – either from what they remembered in conversation, or included in the audits they did in preparation for the interview. We then bolstered this information with the help of online sources. As a result, the lists are not complete. Indeed, to achieve completeness, more effort would be required from infrastructures to comprehensively establish and log what is on their systems, including libraries, and the software installed by users.

In discussions of **critical software**, the theme of ‘negative consequences’ was useful in terms of conceptualising the severity of failure, timescales, and who the failure affects to what degree – all of which are dimensions that could be considered in any risk assessment. Discussion of the challenges around ‘no viable alternative’ touched on the causes of failure (related to risk discussed later), and the effort required to remedy failure. This is useful because it indicates the resources required to address software failure, which can support funding applications.

The most involved discussions were around **risks** to critical software. A lack of maintenance of software either from developers or communities was the biggest concern, and not something easily addressed by infrastructures. However, being aware of how software is maintained could lead to better planning for replacing software when required. There was concern for the support available for software, whether paid or from RSEs, which was linked to the resources infrastructures had available. Also related to funding was concern for licence price changes. Not being aware of licence decisions, alongside other governance issues such as product roadmaps, were flagged as being of concern. Security failure and the use of incorrect/immature code were both risks that might be mitigated with more resources allocated to testing and Validation & Verification (V&V). Reported risks differed in nature for different infrastructures, depending on their funding, size, and place in their life cycle. Well-funded infrastructures like Isambard-AI have been able to pay for licences and support in their capital expenditure, therefore mitigating risk and operational costs. Others have not and rely on their limited operational expenditure to address risks.

The data on software stacks, critical software and risk all point to the benefits of developing robust **audit** processes to improve prevention and mitigation of risk, and better plan for resource requests and allocation. While the infrastructures interviewed all had some form of audit/risk assessment, none had a well-established and regular formal auditing process. However, the work that some had done on categorising what information should be captured (e.g., licensing, support, maintenance), risk severity and time sensitivity all serve as a starting point for any template used by UKRI DRI investments.

Figure 1. Risks to Software

Recommendations

Our recommendations focus primarily on supporting software audits as a means of assessing risk and aiding the prioritisation of resource allocation, as well as supporting funding bids. We also suggest a number of other interventions.

With many of the findings pointing to the benefits of conducting software audits, we recommend that regular audits should be part of an infrastructure's work schedule. Figure 2 is a flow chart of actions if a piece of software fails. Intervening by conducting an audit prior to failure means infrastructures will be more aware of if a failure is likely to happen and understand the scale of failure. They will have an idea of if a failure can be repaired, and if not, have thought about the viable alternatives. If no repair or viable alternative is thought possible, mitigation steps can be taken that might involve stepping in to support software, or applying for funds to develop alternatives.

We suggest that any process should be tailored to the type of infrastructure, and where it is in its life cycle. Those in their early stages should properly assess what goes into the infrastructure before committing, while more established infrastructures need to consider how their existing software is governed and maintained, as well as its ongoing suitability for the infrastructure as technology evolves. GPU-based systems might require more frequent audits as the related software evolves quickly compared to CPU infrastructures. [Appendix C](#) shows one idea for a generic audit process, although further work needs to be done with stakeholders to understand priorities and the effort involved.

There will be a cost to fund any audit process, representing a particular challenge for those infrastructures that have small operational budgets. However, we argue that the cost of auditing an infrastructure should be seen as an investment that can save effort later if software were to unexpectedly become unusable. If UKRI can recommend or provide an audit template tailored to the type of infrastructure and life cycle stage, as well as guidance on how to conduct it, the process could be less burdensome. In planning this support, we suggest that UKRI conducts consultations with infrastructures to understand how best to integrate an audit into their workflows.

We also recommend other support for DRI infrastructures:

- Support information sharing between infrastructures so that there is wider knowledge of risks such as security concerns and software governance decisions. This could be as part of a comprehensive community organisation along the lines of the Society of RSE, or a simple Slack workspace or email list.
- Thought should be given to succession planning for getting people from the UK research community on decision-making boards. For example, the Fortran working group where UK representation is from people of retirement age. Similarly, representation on advisory boards for commonly-used software platforms and standards bodies for key infrastructural software and software formats.
- Invest in training and resources for proper testing and validation & verification (V&V) to ensure software is of good quality. This is especially important for code developed from research grants that lack the resources of other software providers.

Finally, it is important to emphasise the limited scope of this study. More work is needed to more comprehensively understand the landscape for different types of Compute and Data infrastructures, as well the broader community who are using research software on their own computers. We believe that our methodology ([Appendix A](#)) can be scaled up to achieve this, bolstered by any intervention that supports an audit process.

Figure 2. Software Failure and remedy flowchart

Detailed Findings

We now present our detailed findings. We explore participants' understanding of 'critical software', discuss the risks to software identified by participants, and outline what was said about audits.

Throughout, we feature critical software case studies which illustrate key issues with reference to software identified in the data.

Definitions of 'critical software'

With no agreed definition of what 'critical software' means, we asked participants for their interpretations. Within both interviews and focus groups, participants answered this question in two main ways. First, they discussed the theme in terms of there being no viable alternative to a piece of software, given resource restraints. Second, they talked about criticality as the negative consequences of a piece of software no longer functioning.

No viable alternative

Five of the six infrastructures and both focus groups discussed how a piece of software should be classed as critical if there is no viable alternative to it being used. Non-viability here relates to the time or financial constraints of the infrastructure, where having to make changes to software causes substantial disruption because money or effort has to be reallocated from its planned use, or found from new sources.

ARCHER2 described the disruption that can be caused if a piece of software suddenly stops being maintained and gets deprecated, meaning they have to switch to an alternative. They stated that the effort is 'not [just] to change a line in a config. It's possibly a couple of months' effort, possibly a year's effort'. JASMIN illustrated the complexity of the task of having to change to alternative software, describing how some software can be integral to working practices: 'It's costly in terms of time because it's the things that we built practice around... [it impacts] loads of things we do'. A Compute focus group participant highlighted the impact on their service if software has stopped working, saying that the 'huge amount of effort' isn't the best use of their team's resources, which should be focused on 'helping our communities and delivering performance and functionality from an application's perspective'. Isambard-AI argued that at times, there truly is no alternative due to the way hardware is reliant on the software that is provided

alongside it: 'We rely on HPE to provide the firmware, drivers, security patches and updates for Slingshot. They are critical but we do not have choices'. They felt that these restrictions were built into the infrastructure from its conception, and they were not able to choose open source alternatives. Less critical but still problematic, the infrastructure users in the Data focus group mentioned Python libraries. They discussed how if they disappeared, users would find doing their work a lot more time consuming as they would have to find other sources of code, or write it themselves.

Consequences

Second, 'critical software' was discussed in terms of the consequences of software no longer working. Three infrastructures explicitly discussed critical software in terms of the negative consequences of it failing. For example, DARE-UK considered the most extreme cases, saying:

A critical piece of software is essentially software that can't fail and will have catastrophic implications if it does

PSDI discussed this with more nuance, considering how failing software might impact the infrastructure at different levels. They argued that different 'levels of criticality' correspond to failing software that could either take out the whole system, a particular service, or degrade something but not take it out of service. PSDI also brought in a time dimension, distinguishing between 'immediately critical', meaning it is on the verge of breaking, and knowing it is going to break in a few months so needs upgrading. ARCHER2 also discussed the negative impact that software failure would have on their users.

There was discussion about the knock-on consequences of software not working if other software depended on it or if the software was needed for a user to access the infrastructure. These situations were described in focus groups as 'bottlenecks'. In terms of access, it was mentioned in the Compute focus group that software is a bottleneck if through it, 'your relationship with [the infrastructure] is existential'. For example, a participant talked about SSH, saying that if: 'SSH is not supporting the kind of client that you've got, then you don't get to play anything else after that. You might not even be able to discover where the infrastructure is right for you... [It's something] that you need to have in order to even make judgments about whether it's relevant'. PSDI talked about a bottleneck in terms of if 'critical' layers like 'the Kubernetes layer... the fundamental databases', were to fail, then 'that's likely to take down the whole or a large part of the whole system'.

Software: Kubernetes

Issue: Critical to functioning of infrastructure

[Kubernetes](#) is an open source software system for automating software deployment, scaling and management that is widely used by many different organisations. Originally developed by Google, it is now maintained by a global community of contributors under the auspices of the Cloud Native Computing Foundation. It is used in HPC to efficiently manage containerised applications, ensuring consistent environments across nodes and simplifying the deployment of complex workflows. Depending on how Kubernetes is used in an HPC, its failure could result in services becoming unavailable, and disrupt research pipelines or access to tools. More seriously, it could prevent new jobs from starting, interrupt container-based workflows, and cause monitoring, scaling, or recovery mechanisms to break down.

Criticality was at times discussed along an axis of how severe the consequences are versus how many people it affects. In the Compute focus group, a participant argued that it is not just the 'raw usage' (how widespread its usage is) that is important to consider, but how consequential it would be for a small number of users if the software stopped working. This indicates the need to consider both the smooth running of the system for a broad user base (something might break and not be very consequential), and the critical function of some of the software for a small group of users.

Risk factors

Having discussed what 'critical software' means to them, participants were asked about the risks to software. We report on seven main themes: maintenance, a lack of skilled staff, licensing, support, governance, security failure, and incorrect/immature code. In addition, a number of lesser-mentioned risks are summarised. The risks discussed were at times hypothetical, and if they were to occur, might not lead to consequences that could damage the whole system, but rather could take out a specific service or degrade the user experience. Participants also distinguished between immediate or future concerns. These nuances correspond to what PSDI said about 'levels of criticality' and are important to consider as they can help to prioritise resource allocation.

Maintenance

A lack of reliable software maintenance was the most discussed risk among interviews and focus groups. This included concerns about individuals being burdened with maintaining open source code, short-term research funding not supporting maintenance beyond the end of a project, geopolitical tensions, and a lack of UK involvement about the future direction of established tools.

A popular concern was that a key piece of software is being maintained by individuals. This was raised in the Data focus group, with someone saying: 'we all know at least one software project which is being maintained by one dude that does it in his spare time, and if he ever retires we're all going to be absolutely stuffed'. Isambard-AI referenced the famous XKCD comic saying it is like 'that little brick in the big stack of things, and [if] that person in the middle of nowhere wasn't doing their job the whole system collapsed'.

Another concern was the consequences of short-term funding, where maintenance of software ends despite it being vital for people's work. Isambard-AI discussed the case of the NMAC micromagnetic simulation framework, saying: 'Funding stopped... cutting funding meant developers couldn't work on it, and then it became harder and harder to get it working on systems. The same concern was raised in the Data focus group, where they discussed software that was developed for research but is no longer funded: '[What's] at the forefront of anyone's mind is, how is it going to be maintained?... When stuff like this is formed on the back of research funding, it's really difficult to transition to a different funding model'.

Software: NMAG

Issue: End of funding for research-led software development

[NMAG](#), an open-source micromagnetic simulation package developed at the University of Southampton, is an example of software that was developed by researchers and adopted more widely before funding ended. The last software release was in January 2012 when active development ceased. In 2016, the developers reported its still increasing use, despite there being no support available. Its continued use since maintenance ended represents an increasing risk for researchers.

However, Seshat (iDAH) argued that maintaining all old software would be unsustainable, and decisions needed to be made about what UKRI should continue to support.

A focus group participant raised the risk of errors in code that was developed for one project and then used more widely without proper maintenance and testing: 'We build these very rickety, brittle tools and maintaining over the long term is almost impossible. People just come and add and add and add... no one is checking.'

Supporting this argument from another perspective, a RSE participant in the Data focus group raised the concern that they are required to continue to support old software because they cannot get their community to switch away from something: 'so you end up, not only having to develop new stuff, but you're having to maintain the old stuff as well'. Ongoing maintenance was raised by another RSE participant, saying their managers encourage them to develop open source without realising the burden it creates in maintaining it, which can lead to problems: 'it's not really a key part of my job role, so that can be quite tricky'.

ARCHER2 contrasted the UK's inconsistent efforts to build and maintain software with the US situation, where national labs have come together with government departments to strategically support critical software. They discussed how the UK had been successful with this sort of work in the past – highlighting the Grid Core programme in the early 2000s – but that this sort of work has relied on short-term grant funding rather than sustainable strategic funding.

Another cause for concern was geopolitical upheaval, with discussions about the war in Ukraine meaning Ukrainian software is no longer maintained, and Russian developed software not used due to security concerns. The Trump administration's threats to the survival of science organisations was also flagged as a concern.

Finally, ARCHER2 argued that if software is well-supported by other industries (e.g., C++ in computer games) or countries (often the USA), then there is little risk

in using that software in their infrastructure. However, they did flag that in these sorts of cases the UK has a lack of representation on the decision-making panels on key software. They raise the issue of Fortran where the UK lacks personnel on standards boards, and the people we do have are approaching retirement, with no succession plan in place.

Software: Fortran

Issue: Maintaining UK input into future direction

Fortran remains vital to UK research due to its efficiency in numerical computing, legacy codebases, and support for high-performance computing. It underpins key scientific packages and libraries in fields like climate modelling, chemistry and physics, with widespread institutional expertise and global collaboration needs reinforcing its use. Modernisation of the Fortran standard keeps it relevant for supercomputing applications, overseen by the ISO/IEC [Fortran Working Group](#). The UK has traditionally had strong representation on this working group; with several officers. However, many current members are now retired and it is unclear if there needs to be a formal plan to ensure that the requirements of the UK community are represented in changes to the language, particularly around optimised support for new platforms and tools.

Table 2. Maintenance challenges

Issue	Challenge
Software maintained by small number of people	Software is no longer supported if a person/ people move on or retire
End of short-term funding	Software is no longer maintained once funding ends
RSEs required to maintain old code	A very time consuming task not core to the role
No UK strategic funding for development and maintenance	Software is developed as part of short term grants, without a longer term plan
Geopolitical instability	Software can suddenly become unmaintained or unsafe
Lack of UK representation on decision-making panels	Software is developed in a way that does not support UK DRI

Lack of skilled staff

Related to maintenance, a lack of skilled staff was said to be a risk to the running of the infrastructures. These examples highlight that people – as well as software and hardware – are important investments.

Seshat (iDAH) highlighted that a lack of regular funding has meant they have struggled to employ RSEs for set up and maintenance. A participant in the data focus group discussed the lack of funding for a pipeline of support staff, arguing this is: 'absolutely fundamental... It underpins all of this. Some of these projects will go on, not just for [more than] three years... and we have to think about what's the next load of staff that are going to be coming in to allow us to continue to develop'.

User-participants in the Compute focus group discussed the importance of access to infrastructure technical support and documentation. This is important because, in one participant's words, they are 'not, on the whole, highly technically competent [and] are very reliant on HPC services... having people who can help us install our codes'. However, they were concerned that at times staff had not had enough training in the latest 'bleeding edge' technologies to help them, which had impacted their research.

Licensing

Many participants were concerned about software licensing. Changes to pricing (from free to paid or costs increasing) was the main concern, with other issues around the politics of licenses and compliance with legislation also raised.

The archetypal cautionary tale of licence changes was of Conda, which last year appeared to change to a paid licence for research staff. Isambard-AI highlighted how this was unexpected because people did not question the governance, and did not expect things to change: 'people didn't look too much, and you were told in a blogpost... it completely changed at the drop of a hat because the governance allowed them to do that, and therefore you were exposed to that risk'.

Software: Conda and the Anaconda repository

Issue: Licence terms uncertain

Academics became concerned when Anaconda [updated its terms of service](#) in March 2024 to restrict commercial use of the packages in its Anaconda repository without a paid licence. Although the free version of Anaconda in the Community Repository remained available for individual and academic use, the language of the new terms created confusion and uncertainty and some common non-free packages were also mirrored in the free repository. Many feared potential legal or financial implications for using Conda, the package manager used to install packages from either of the repositories in research projects, HPC infrastructures or teaching environments. The lack of clear initial communication led to mistrust, prompting discussions about open alternatives and a shift toward more transparent packaging ecosystems.

While this change to Conda ultimately did not affect researchers, changes to licence pricing are a risk as infrastructure budgets could struggle to absorb a price increase. JASMIN identify VMware as a concern, indicating how it is 'critical software' because it is a lot of effort to replace:

The way that the price went up last year has shocked us to a point where if they did the same thing again, we just couldn't afford to do that and it would be a huge amount of effort to migrate to something that there isn't really a competitor for.

As a result of being caught up in this uncertainty, JASMIN now leans toward using open source software, supported by community or service agreements.

Software: VMware

Issue: Licence price increase

VMware, a developer of virtualisation and cloud computing solutions, has traditionally offered various licensing models including perpetual licenses and subscription-based options. However, following Broadcom's acquisition of VMware in 2023, [substantial changes](#) were implemented in VMware's licensing structure. These included moving exclusively to subscription models that increased costs for many customers, a change from per-CPU to per-core licensing (disproportionately affecting large DRIs), and the ending of academic discounts. These changes have prompted concerns within the UK academic community about financial sustainability and the feasibility of transitioning to alternative platforms.

Seshat (iDAH) highlighted how small AHRC-funded projects like themselves are paying licences for Azure storage. With the infrastructure's uncertain funding, they saw a risk to being able to continue to pay for this service.

A participant in the Data focus group highlighted the risk of changes to licences as software matures: 'They swap features between their columns of how they're [charging for] them... It's quite frustrating... we've had to change the whole of our client-side infrastructure off the back of RStudio changing what is available'.

Away from cost, another participant raised an interesting point about licences and compliance, describing how some of the software licences for federated data access don't define how they are adhering to the relevant legislation and compliance. With work in personal health data needing to be secure, using this software is a risk to the infrastructure's reputation, not to mention the public's data.

Support

In discussions that overlapped with those about licensing, participants

shared their experiences of paid support. Experiences varied depending on how well infrastructures were funded for both capital costs and day-to-day maintenance, with an increased risk to infrastructure when support was not available.

Well-resourced infrastructures could include support costs in their capital expenditure, eliminating the need to pay for day-to-day maintenance of the software. JASMIN argued this removes the responsibility from members of staff who might move on and leave the infrastructure exposed through lack of oversight. As ARCHER2 put it 'we pay the license [with support]... and they are responsible for maintaining the software'. Isambard-AI concurred, and also explained that they have service agreements with much of their software because the reputational cost of such a well-funded infrastructure failing is too high.

When support was not purchased, DARE-UK and PSDI were concerned about the cost of operating open source software without a service agreement. PSDI stated 'you don't spend the money on buying the big licence [and support], but you do spend the money on trying to maintain it... That's the trade-off'. By not paying for support in capital expenditure, the cost of effort eats into operational budgets. Due to lack of funding, Seshat (iDAH) were unable to pay for support for the open source software that they use, instead relying on GitHub to flag things which RSEs addressed on an ad-hoc basis. With funding for their RSE support ending, there is a clear risk to the stability of the infrastructure.

Governance

Governance was discussed in relation to licensing, maintenance and the future direction of software. While these issues are risks in themselves, a lack of understanding of governance should be considered a form of risk as it acts to blind infrastructures to the threats it faces.

Some infrastructures sought out information on governance. DARE-UK identified the kinds of things that are useful to know, asking 'if this is open source, who's behind it? What's the community look like? How mature is it? What's the development team like? What's its roadmap?' PSDI thought along similar lines, identifying what software is likely to carry less risk due to how it is licenced and supported.

Another way to mitigate this risk is to be involved in governance decisions. However, as identified above, there is often a lack of UK involvement in these governance boards. This is also a very effort-heavy strategy, and without effective knowledge sharing, is of limited impact.

When there is no capacity to do either of these things, infrastructures might try to mitigate risk of the unknown by using well-established products. Seshat

(iDAH) took this approach, saying they ‘only work with relatively household names, and we assume they are well-supported. Everyone is using them, and they will not turn to the dark side [become paid], let’s say, or disappear and so on. If that happens, we hope it’s so generic that we can just move to a different provider’.

Security failure

A keenly felt risk was that of security failure. Participants discussed the consequences of security failures when dealing with sensitive data, the problem of malicious code, and issues with not knowing what users were installing.

DARE-UK highlighted the consequences of security failure in Trusted Research Environments, discussed both in terms of financial liability and the impact it would have on the subject:

The impact is four per cent in turnover or £18 million or whatever the fine is, but that’s neither here nor there compared to the impact on the subject. If it’s a smallish list from the witness protection programme, you have put people’s lives really at risk by doing this.

Focus group participants who worked in health research shared similar concerns, flagging that software developers might not take security into account, but this is one of the most important things for people working with sensitive data.

A participant from the Data focus group raised the impact of malicious code. They were unaware that they were using a piece of software, Log4j, with a security flaw, until something was flagged during a migration. As a consequence they had to change ‘the whole workflow’ for some of their tools, and adapt and find alternative solutions, which they said was a challenge. Isambard-AI also referred to a security flaw in a recent news item regarding an open-source project which resulted in open-source community security concerns.

Software: Log4j

Issue: Security Failure

The [Log4j vulnerability](#) was a critical security flaw in the widely used open source Java logging library, Log4j. Discovered in December 2021, it allowed unauthenticated remote code execution by logging a specially crafted string, enabling attackers to install malware, steal data, or gain control over affected systems. This flaw impacted numerous applications and services that utilize Log4j, including major tech companies like Amazon Web Services, Microsoft, and IBM. It also affected UK academic infrastructures, sometimes indirectly due to its use by data analytics platforms installed on the infrastructures such as Apache Spark. Organisations were required to update to the latest Log4j version and apply security patches to mitigate any risk.

Both JASMIN and Isambard-AI reported having little oversight of what their users install, relying on them adhering to the terms of and conditions of use. JASMIN argued that due to their resource constraints, they had to 'push that responsibility out to [the users] because that would be too big a job to try and manage all of that'. As a result, there is a risk that users might install software that are nefarious, or pose ethical questions such as modelling viruses. This is not only a threat to the reputation of the instructure, but could also damage it if that infrastructure is connected to physical research infrastructure such as laboratory control systems.

Incorrect/immature code

Incorrect and immature code were discussed as a risk to both the stability of the infrastructure and the quality of the research it generates.

A participant in the Compute focus group discussed how there is a risk to research software producing accurate results if the code that is used is not correct, saying 'the nightmare scenario is that five years on you discover it was a bug that gave the wrong answer'. This speaks to the need for effective testing, and Verification and Validation (V&V). However, these require effort, as well as people having the right knowledge and experience. One participant argued for the need to track code's provenance so it can be determined where an issue arose, but another suggested doing so could be politically difficult, as 'you will not have too many friends at the end of the process because everybody thinks they already do things perfectly'.

DARE-UK discussed the importance of using mature and well-tested open source software, rather than risking the use of a research prototype from a university. In their context, they thought this especially important if the software is used to link different Trusted Research Environments together, as data security is such a concern.

Other risks

There were a number of other risks that were raised less often, or did not directly relate to software. These were changing trends in platforms, software changing functionality, downtime and lack of connectivity, and how an infrastructure is set up.

The change from CPU to GPU in compute infrastructure was considered a risk by ARCHER2 who noted the need to support the implementation of research applications on GPU machines: 'A lot of these codes are going to struggle, if they do not have complete and functional GPU implementations. They will have no home in the UK, which is a big threat'. This view was echoed in the Compute focus

group.

Also thinking in the medium to long term, PSDI mentioned that as software gets upgraded, its use might change, requiring effort to make it work in the infrastructure, or even making it no longer fit-for-purpose.

There was concern that downtime or lack of connectivity might impact users' trust in the infrastructure. Isambard-AI's choice to use well-supported cloud services such as AWS rather than on-prem servers limited this risk. Two Data focus group participants highlighted how poor connectivity was a risk to their work in the Global South or remote Antarctic stations. This was seen as a problem because most services are geared towards good bandwidth where large software updates might 'flood the link'. One participant argued that tools like SSH and Rsync are critical because they work well over very low bandwidth connections. While edge cases, they are important to consider for the work that these researchers do.

Finally, participants in the Compute focus group identified that the way an infrastructure is set up can limit its applications for users. They discussed how UK infrastructures' use of APIs in workflows is limited due to compute nodes being behind firewalls: 'You've got no access to the internet from a compute node, but there can be competitors out there for whom that's not true'. Someone else discussed the challenges of collaborating across different infrastructures where researchers need to use CPU-based compute in one place, GPU-compute elsewhere, and the data needs to be moved around and tracked effectively. A third participant commented on the fact that workflows involve multiple types of hardware and software including HPC and cloud compute, and trying to optimise effort and energy usage is a challenge.

Cross-cutting themes

We identify two cross-cutting issues that underlay many of the risks discussed: insufficient and inconsistent funding, and a lack of risk assessment/auditing.

A lack of funding can mean that licenses for reliable and well maintained software are not affordable, and support for open source software cannot be purchased. When these mitigations against risk are not in place, the funds for in-house maintenance might also not be available. Short-term funding leads to infrastructures relying on software that is no longer supported, and more broadly, strategic funding of the development of nationally important DRI is missing. For users, low/no resources for adequate testing, and verification & validation can lead to inaccurate code.

As a result of insufficient risk assessment/auditing, software governance can be misunderstood leaving infrastructures vulnerable to sudden changes to licenses

or maintenance, and not understanding a software's longer-term roadmap. Security vulnerabilities might also be missed. Any assessment would of course require effort, which has to be funded.

While funding issues are challenging to address and beyond our influence, we suggest that the relatively small cost of auditing an infrastructure's software would be an effective way to prepare for and mitigate risks to digital research infrastructure. We discuss audits now.

Audits

Being aware of risk factors can allow infrastructures to plan effectively for their mitigation. One way of doing this is through an audit process.

Interviewees talked about the extent to which they conduct auditing activities. PSDI prepared for the interview by asking staff details of software that were considered important, and then collectively assessing different criteria. As mentioned earlier, they defined different 'levels of criticality' corresponding to failing software that could either take out the whole system, a particular service, or degrade something but not take it out of service. They also brought in a time dimension, distinguishing between 'immediately critical', meaning it is on the verge of breaking, and knowing it is going to break in a few months so needs upgrading. They sought out information on licensing; whether open source, freemium, commercial license, or any other license conditions, as well as trying to understand the maintenance; whether it was a supported open source project, a wide IT community, supported by a particular company, or by the particular science domain.

ARCHER2 explained that for them, there are different processes for keeping track of their software depending on the different layers of the stack. Low-level software is looked after through contracts with the hardware vendors, while ARCHER2 monitors the rest of the stack. Before the interview, staff conducted a short audit of the software they considered to be critical. They distinguished between software which was not a priority for funding because it was supported well outside of the UK, and the software that they flagged as in need of UK funding for maintenance.

Other infrastructures had not conducted any sort of formal audit, relying instead on the expertise of their staff and the way researchers use the service: 'I think there's a common understanding amongst [the] team of what the infrastructure is, what the software is used for, and the things that we use to deploy big systems'. One infrastructure explained that while they control the software below the user level, they do not have full knowledge of what software users are installing on virtual machines: 'We have to push that responsibility out to them really, because that would be too big a job to try and manage all of that'. While relying on staff and users to keep track of software makes the need for a formal audit less urgent, operating in this way does expose infrastructures to risk if their staff leave or users do not follow good practice.

Both DARE-UK and Isambard-AI are early on in their life cycle so have not needed to conduct audits. Nevertheless, they were able to share their thoughts on the process. DARE-UK commented about risk assessment in an audit. While they had not done this yet, they suggested that Trusted Research Environments (TRE) could

test vulnerabilities on a distributed testbed, or bring in assessors from GCHQ or the National Cyber Security Centre. Isambard-AI discussed the challenge of doing an audit on an infrastructure that is subject to so much rapid change, saying the fast pace of change in AI hardware/software (e.g., Nvidia) makes it necessary to do an audit every 6 months.

Some infrastructures suggested ideas for improving DRI audits. PSDI suggested an audit framework would have helped steer their thinking and encouraged them to focus on the things that are a priority for UKRI. DARE-UK and ARCHER2 thought that standardising risk assessment across all DRI investments would be useful. Rather than 'reinventing wheels', DARE-UK suggested using the National Cyber Security Centre (NCSC) cyber assessment framework or drawing on ISO 27001 Information Security Management tools. ARCHER2 suggested UKRI use Business Continuity and Disaster Recovery (BCDR) consultants to design a template for investments to use. ARCHER2 also suggested it was important to consider the role of international coordination and collaboration when surveying critical software in order to reveal where UK support is needed. Finally, PSDI suggested enhancing their current audit with information on when software needs to be upgraded or replaced.

Focus groups were enthusiastic about the value of an audit, and discussed what they thought would be useful to include.

Staff suggested including:

- An assessment of security – Conduct tests to assess how well the system holds up.
- Detail the 'chain' of software associated with the software of interest, including information on licenses.
- The Technological Readiness Level (TRL) for software, and whether that is appropriate for that level of the infrastructure – Something unproven in the lower levels could be more of a risk than some research software developed by the researcher).
- Detail of how the software will continue to be supported and maintained.
- Usage rates of software to indicate priorities for investment.

Users' suggestions included:

- An assessment of security when using the infrastructure for research.
- An assessment of software's compliance to certain standards – Is the software safe to use in certain fields e.g., health data?
- Detail of what support and training is available (for users of the software) - to

appear on the website.

- Detail of how the software will continue to be supported and maintained.
- An assessment of the quality of the application software – is the code correct? Has it gone through verification and validation testing?
- Details of the environmental impact of the usage.
- Details of the performance of the infrastructure

In summary, those infrastructures that conducted an audit of some sort valued the experience, providing some good practice to follow and suggesting how processes could be developed and improved. There was also enthusiasm for this sort of work from the focus groups, including the users.

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Appendix A - Methodology

Our research was designed to capture perspectives on ‘critical software’ for UKRI DRI investments. It consisted of a short qualitative study over the first 3 months of 2025, involving 6 online interviews with 14 staff of UKRI DRI investments, and 2 focus groups with 13 representatives of the wider research community. First, UKRI DRI set up interviews with 3 Compute infrastructures and 3 Data infrastructures. We conducted one interview per infrastructure with either an individual, a pair, or a small group. We asked participants about the software in their stack including details of licences, maintenance and funding. We also asked what software they consider to be ‘critical’ to the running of their infrastructure, how they assess risk to this software, and if/how they audit their software. Participants also had the opportunity to raise other issues related to their perception of critical software. Following interviews, we arranged focused groups with the wider community of staff and researchers who run or use UKRI digital research infrastructures. Focus groups discussed similar themes, and elicited reflections from the interviews to act as a sense-check for the small sample size. These two research methods allowed us to address our research questions, providing UKRI DRI with recommendations for policy and practice.

Ethics

Approval for the study was sought from the University of Southampton’s ethics committee. Prior to interview, potential participants were provided with an information sheet and consent form that provided details about the aims of the research, the interview process (such as audio/video recording and transcription), confidentiality and anonymisation processes, and data storage and archiving. While the investments are named in the report, anonymity of participants was emphasised as we wanted them to feel they could speak freely about their perceptions. Participants completed an email consent form. Interviews were transcribed, and transcripts pseudonymised and retained for archiving in a University of Southampton data repository.

Recruitment and sample

The research team and UKRI DRI identified a selection of investments that would provide views from both Compute and Data infrastructures. These investments were approached by UKRI DRI, with staff deciding who would be best placed to take part in the interview. The infrastructures included in the study were ARCHER2, DARE-UK, Seshat (iDAH), Isambard-AI, JASMIN and PSDI. Details of these infrastructures are detailed in Table 1.

Table 3. Maintenance challenges

Name	Type	Description	Location	Funding
ARCHER2	Compute	UK National Supercomputing Service	University of Edinburgh	£79M from EPSRC and NERC.
Isambard-AI	Compute	UK's largest AI-focused supercomputer. Phase 1: 168 NVIDIA Grace-Hopper GPUs, direct liquid cooled. Phase 2: 5280 NVIDIA Grace-Hopper GPUs, direct liquid cooled.	National Composites Centre, Bristol	£225M from UK Government.
JASMIN	Compute	High-performance data analysis facility for environmental science, funded primarily by NERC and operated by STFC. Co-located with (and hosts) CEDA Archive, a key part of NERC's Environmental Data Service.	RAL, Harwell Campus, Oxfordshire UK	£9M (FY 23/24-24/25) from UKRI DRI.
DARE-UK	Compute	Connects national network of secure and public-focused sensitive data research infrastructures.	Health Data Research UK, London	£10.1M (FY 23/24-24/25) from UKRI DRI.
Seshat (iDAH)	Data	Seshat Global History Databank, part of iDAH, a national infrastructure for digital innovation and curation for arts and humanities.	The Alan Turing Institute	Overall funding for iDAH £3.3M (FY 23/24-24/25) from UKRI DRI. Seshat's funding was due to run out 31/3/25.
PSDI	Data	A data infrastructure that brings together and builds upon the various data systems researchers currently use in the physical sciences.	Rutherford Appleton Laboratory	£3.3M (FY 23/24-24/25) from UKRI DRI.

All interview participants had first-hand experience of working with the investments. Their names and details of their roles have been withheld to reduce the risk of their identities being revealed.

Recruitment for focus groups was achieved through an online expression of interest form promoted through UKRI networks. This gathered 73 responses, indicating a healthy interest in the research topic. We aimed to have focus groups of eight, with a balance of people from different types of infrastructure, different disciplines, and different career stages. In the end, focus group 1 featured 6 participants linked to Compute infrastructures and focus group 2 had 7 participants from Data infrastructures. Participants information has been anonymised, but some indicative information is shared in Table 2.

Table 4. Focus Group Participant Info

Role (self-described)	Focus	Career Stage
RSE & Researcher	Compute	Phase 2 - Early (e.g., Research Assistant/Associate, first grant holder, Lecturer)
Researcher	Compute	Phase 2 - Early (e.g., Research Assistant/Associate, first grant holder, Lecturer)
RSE & Researcher	Compute	Phase 2 - Early (e.g., Research Assistant/Associate, first grant holder, Lecturer)
Computational Scientist	Compute	Phase 3 - Mid/Recognised (e.g., Senior lecturer, Reader, Senior Researcher, Associate Professor)
RSE, Infrastructure engineer	Compute	Phase 3 - Mid/Recognised (e.g., Senior lecturer, Reader, Senior Researcher, Associate Professor)
Researcher	Compute	Phase 4 - Established/Experienced/Senior (e.g., Professor, Director of Research)
PhD researcher	Data	Phase 1 - Junior (e.g., PhD Candidate)
Data management specialist	Data	Phase 2 - Early (e.g., Research Assistant/Associate, first grant holder, Lecturer)
Data professional & grant application advisor	Data	Phase 3 - Mid/Recognised (e.g., Senior lecturer, Reader, Senior Researcher, Associate Professor)
Researcher	Data	Phase 3 - Mid/Recognised (e.g., Senior lecturer, Reader, Senior Researcher, Associate Professor)
Data professional	Data	Phase 3 - Mid/Recognised (e.g., Senior lecturer, Reader, Senior Researcher, Associate Professor)
RSE & PI	Data	Phase 3 - Mid/Recognised (e.g., Senior lecturer, Reader, Senior Researcher, Associate Professor)
Data professional	Data	Phase 4 - Established/Experienced/Senior (e.g., Professor, Director of Research)

The interviews

The interviews were designed to last between 45 minutes and 1 hour, and were conducted online following a semi-structured topic guide. We asked participants about their role and about their infrastructure, details of the software that runs on different layers of their software stack, their perspective on what should be considered critical software, their perspectives on the risks to the infrastructure's smooth operation, and details about any audit processes that might take place.

The focus groups

The focus groups were designed to last for around 2 hours, and were also conducted online. We posed a series of questions to the focus groups based on each of the main themes that emerged from interviews, namely: What software do you use?; What do you consider to be 'critical software' and why?; What are the risk factors to consider regarding software?; and What does/should an audit look like for the infrastructure(s) you are involved in? Participants were invited to answer individually, and then given the opportunity to discuss each others' responses. While we purposefully constrained the scope of the focus group through the questions we posed, we did not then aim for consensus positions. Rather, we sought data to flesh out the themes from interviews in order to try and confirm that the data were representative of the staff and user communities.

Data analysis

After transcription of the audio recording, interviews and focus groups were coded in Atlas.ti, qualitative data analysis (QDA) software. We first coded to broad thematic and descriptive codes reflecting the interview and focus group themes. These included details of infrastructures and their software, perceptions of what 'critical software' is, perceptions of risks to software and infrastructures, opinions on audits, and contextual information. Later, more fine-grained coding captured the themes that emerged relating to how participants defined 'critical software' and the risks to software and infrastructures. These codes enabled us to analyse and understand the role of various software in the smooth running of DRI infrastructures, the risks to that software, and what can be done to prepare infrastructures to more effectively prepare for and mitigate against these risks.

It is important to note that due to the small sample size for both interviews and focus groups, some issues discussed in the findings were only raised by a small number of participants. We have included them in the report due to our perception that they are important, but more in-depth work is needed to understand if they are a concern to the wider community.

Appendix B - Infrastructure software stacks (reported)

Each infrastructure interviewed provided examples of software present at different levels of their software stack. These have been categorised for simplicity of comparison, particularly to identify where there may be commonalities and to understand how the risks can be assessed.

The stack can be generalised into the following layers:

- **Applications:** this is the layer that the users of the infrastructure have most control and choice over and is typically most discipline specific. It includes categories such as research applications and research databases, data conversion tools, workflow management, and remote access tools.
- **Programming environment:** this is the layer that enables a user to make use of the infrastructure and is typically tailored to the type of infrastructure. It includes categories such as compilers, libraries, programming models, programming languages, development tools, database systems, and data analytics.
- **Resource management:** this is the layer that enables the operation of the infrastructure as a service for users. It includes categories such as job schedulers, container orchestration / management, configuration management, package management systems, and data transfer.
- **System management:** this is the layer that interfaces with the hardware, and is often not research specific though there is some software which targets high performance. It includes categories such as operating systems, device drivers, data storage, and virtualisation.
- **User management and support:** while not strictly running on the main resource, this set of software is important to enable the infrastructure to provide an effective service to users. It includes categories such as helpdesk software and collaboration software.

The following tables are indicative, rather than comprehensive, due to the time limitations during the interviews.

Table 5. Software Stacks

ARCHER2

Layer	Examples
Applications	Blender, CASINO, CASTEP, CESM2, Chemshell, Code_Saturne, CP2K, CRYSTAL, FHI-aims, GROMACS, LAMMPS, MITgcm, Met Office Unified Model, NAMD, Nektar++, NEMO, NWChem, ONETEP, OpenFOAM, ORCA, ParaView, QChem, Quantum Espresso, VASP, Visidata, VMD.
Programming environment	Compilers: AOCC, CCE, GCC. Development Tools: AMD μ Prof, ATP, CrayPAT, Darshan, gdb4hpc, Linaro Forge, STAT, valgrind4hpc Libraries: ADIOS, AOCL, ARPACK-NG, Boost, Eigen, FFTW, GLM, Global Arrays Toolkit, HDF5, HPE Cray MPICH2, HPE Cray OpenSHMEM, HYPRE, libsci (BLAS, LAPACK, BLACS, SCALAPACK). METIS / Parmetis, MUMPS, NetCDF, PETSc, Scotch / PT-Scotch, SLEPc, SuperLU / SuperLU_DIST, Trilinos.
Resource management	Globus, Singularity, Slurm, Spack
System management	Lustre, HPE Cray Linux Environment
User management and support	SAFE

Isambard-AI

Layer	Examples
Applications	AlphaFold
Programming environment	Cray Programming Environment, PyTorch
Resource management	Ansible, Conda, HPE CSM, NVIDIA GPU Cloud, Podman, Slurm
System management	SUSE Linux
User management and support	

JASMIN

Layer	Examples
Applications	Cylc, NV5 IDL
Programming environment	JASPy (Python on JASMIN), Jupyter Notebook
Resource management	Dask Gateway, Globus, GridFTP, Kubernetes, LOTUS, NoMachine, Puppet, Rose, Slurm, SUSE Rancher.
System management	Datacore Swarm for S3, Fedora EPEL, OpenStack Swift, Quoobyte, Rocky Linux 9, VDURA (Panasas), VMware EXSi, VMware vSphere.
User management and support	HelpScout

DARE-UK

The UK's many TREs are built from a wide range of technologies, platforms and application stacks. The examples are non-exhaustive.

Layer	Examples
Applications	GA4GH WfExS, NextFlow, SnakeMake
Programming environment	Language: R, Python, SPSS, Stata, Julia, ... RDBMS: SQL Server, MySQL, PostGres, MongoDB, ... Analytics: Jupyter, SAS, TensorFlow, PyTorch, GA4GH TES, ... DataSHIELD, Bitfount, Vantage6, Databricks, SHAIIP, EHRQL,...
Resource management	App/job: JupyterHub, Slurm, ... Data: minio S3, Snowflake, IQVIA PET, splink, ... Container: Kubernetes, ArgoCD, Docker, Podman, ... Platform: Terraform, ansible, Azure, AWS, GCP, ...
System management	O/S: Linux, Windows. Virtualisation: VMWare, OpenStack, Azure, AWS, GCP, ... Platform: Aridhia, DNA Nexus, ARO, SeRP, ...
User management and support	Keycloak, Entra, AWS IAM, ServiceNow, ...

Seshat (iDAH)

Layer	Examples
Applications	
Programming environment	Django, GitHub
Resource management	Pulumi
System management	Azure
User management and support	

PSDI

Layer	Examples
Applications	Apache Airflow, AiiDA, AMBER, Chemdoodle, CSD, CSD OPTIMADE API, C2X, DAWN, Demeter, Larch, Mantid, Magres Database v1 / v2, Open Babel, OpenMM, OPTIMADE, OPTIMADE-python-tools, Redis. Vue
Programming environment	Data Analysis: ElasticSearch, OpenSearch. Databases: InvenioRDM, MariaDB, MaterialUI, MongoDB, PostGres Libraries: NextJS, Node.js, numpy, PyTorch, React, Strawberry Python Library GitHub
Resource management	Apptainer, Docker, DockerHub, FluxCD, JupyterHub, Kubernetes
System management	Ceph Object Store, OpenStack., ownCloud Infinite Scale, Windows 10/11
User management and support	Keycloak, SATOSA

Appendix C – Lists of software provided by Compute and Data focus groups

Compute

AlphaFold
AMBER
Ansible
Apptainer/Singularity
BioSimGrid
Blender
CASTEP
CHARMM
CMake (open source supported by kitware)
Conda
CONQUEST (GPL)
Containers from NVIDIA GPU Cloud
CP2k GPL
Cray
CSM (Kubernetes)
CUDA libraries (if NVIDIA GPU)
Cylc
Dask Gateway
DL_POLY (GPL)
Docker
EPEL
EXSi
FFT (e.g. FFTE (free source code) or FFTW (GPLv2 or later))
Fftw
FHLaims (paid-for source code distribution)
Fiftyone (commercial, "open core")
Fortran
Globus
Globus vSphere
GNU Make v 4
Grid FTP
GROMACS
GULP (free non commercial)
HelpScout
JIRA
Jupyter hub/lab
Jupyter Notebook
Kubernetes
LAMMPS (GPL)
Lotus
MACE/GAP ML (Cambridge Academic License)
Maths libraries (BLAS, LAPACK, ScaLAPACK)
MPI
NAMD
NoMachine
ONETEP (free non-commercial source code distribution)
openFOAM
OpenMM
OpenStack
Parallel debugger, e.g. DDT
Parallel profiler, e.g. MAP
Paraview (open source supported by kitware)
Parnassus
Podman
Puppet
Python + numpy + scipy
Python NV5 IDL
Python: MACE/GRACE/DPA
PyTorch
Quantum Espresso GPL
Questaal BSD-3
Queuing/job management system
Quobyte
R Studio
Rocky Linux 9
ROCm compiler stack
ROCm libraries (if AMD GPU)
Rose
Slingshot
Slurm
Slurm
SSH Certificates
SUSE Linux
SUSE Rancher (Kubernetes)
Terraform
Timm
torchaudio
VASP
Visual Studio Code
VMWare
VMWare

Data

(ana)Conda environments
1Password
AIIDA
Airflow - for managing processes
AMBER
Ansible
Apache
Apache Airflow
Atomsk
Azure
Bash scripting (file handling, input data reformatting or creation)
BitCurator (digital preservation/recovery)
Browsertrix web archiving
C
C2X
Ceph Object Store
Chemdoodle WordPress
CircleCI
CSV tools e.g. csvkit, xcsv, cassava
Dedicated Java libraries (eg MASON, REPASt)
Demeter Teams, Zoom
Django GitHub
DNAnexus Meridian Azure

Docker Container	Python DAWN
DockerHub	Python libraries
Elasticsearch	Python SQL JSON
eXist-db	PyTorch
FluxCD	QGIS
Galaxy	Qsub
Gary Stringer	R
GCC	R OpenStack (VM provision?)
Git (hub/lab(on prem))	R studio
GitHub	R studio server
GitLab (on prem)	RABBIT
Google suite (commercial)	React
Grafana/Graphite/Carbon	Rsync
Helpdesk system software (presently Help Scout for us)	Rsync, Globus, FTP
IDL - data analysis (commercial)	Satosa
InvenioRDM	Slurm
Javascript	SnakeMake AWS
Javascript - web services	SPSS
Jira	ssh
JIRA - task tracking	ssh
JIRA (tracking features)	STAC - data discovery (open)
Julia	Stata
JupyterHub	Strawberry Python Library
Keycloak	TypeScript
Kubernetes	Various OS software
Larch EventBrite, Miro, Mentimeter	Visual Studio
LaTeX	VMWare
Libre Office	VMWare
Linux	Vue OPTIMADE API
Linux (various flavours, RHEL, Debian)	Web Browser
LLM	Windows 10/11
Mantid Jobe Moodle Zenodo	X-Road
MariaDB	Zoom
MaterialUI	
Matlab - data analysis (commercial)	
mdEditor	
Microsoft PowerPlatform	
Microsoft SharePoint	
Miro - community engagement (commercial)	
MongoDB	
Monitoring tools - e.g. grafana	
MS Office	
netCDF tools e.g. ncdump, nco, panoply, idv	
NetFlow Google Cloud TensorFlow (ML platform)	
NetLogo (to my frustration)	
NextJS	
Nginx	
Node.js	
numpy C++	
NVivo	
Omeka S / Omeka Classic	
Open Babel	
OpenMM	
OpenSearch/ElasticSearch	
OPTIMADE	
OPTIMADE-python-tools Redis	
Oracle/Apex	
otter.ai	
ownCloud Infinite Scale	
Oxygen/XML	
PostGRES	
Postgres	
Pulumi	
Python	

Appendix D – Audit example

Once information on each risk is gathered (e.g., licensing, support, governance, maintenance, security issues), scoring the severity of risk can help to set priorities for interventions.

Table 5. Suggestion for part of a useful audit process

Software	Risks (Scored 1-3)							Overall score
	Availability of support from developers/community	Availability of support from internal staff	Estimation of licensing risk	Availability and cost of commercial support	Estimation of governance risk	Security risk	Estimation of code correctness and maturity	
Example 1	1	3	3	2	2	1	2	14
Example 2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	8